

Vertical Resonance

DANIEL FREDRIKSSON #1, Dalarna University #1, Sweden

PAUL EVANS #2, Dalarna University #1, Sweden

TANJA JÖRGENSEN #3, Dalarna University #1, Sweden

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1 PROGRAM NOTES

In this performance, the NIME-instrument called Evangistrum is utilized together with a Church Organ (or equivalent) to explore the concept of “vertical resonance”: the existential axis of Hartmut Rosas [1] theory of resonance. The Evangistrum is an audiovisual instrument for two performers, designed to promote collaboration, have strong audiovisual congruence and to be intuitive to use while still allowing for more complex levels of expression. The design was built using Unreal Engine, controlled with commercially available midi controllers.

2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The performers set out to learn to play on and with a newly conceived audiovisual instrument. The performance was conceived to further explore the Evangistrums possibilities for collaboration and resonance. It was developed as a composition in three parts, with semi-improvised melodic and rhythmic content. The premiere performance in a local church, and the rehearsals leading up to them, including the composition process, were designed as a micro-study, exploring how to learn to play and create on a newly developed instrument, and for the organist how to learn to play with a newly developed instrument. The Evangistrum was further developed during and between these sessions, relating both to the experience of playing and learning the instrument, as well as to composing the music.

3 PERFORMANCE NOTES

This is a 15 minutes performance for three performers, on two instruments. The length can be adjusted to fit conference schedule.

Instruments:

- (1) “Evangistrum”, an audiovisual instrument built in the Unreal Engine and played with three midi controllers by two persons. The performers will bring everything needed for this of course.
- (2) Church Organ (or equivalent). If a church organ is not present, a good keyboard with organ sound, such as a Nord Stage or similar is quite sufficient. This can be brought by the performers as well if needed.

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Fig. 1. Vertical Resonance performed at Equmeniakyrkan Borlänge, 2023

Venue: A church locale (with an organ) would be amazing for this! However, the performance can take place in any venue with a decent sound system and a projector. Any feasible surface will work for the projected visuals, in the premiere performance the visuals was projected on the church organ pipes to great effect. While the focus of the performance is one of introspection and contemplation, we see no issue performing in a club environment.

4 MEDIA LINKS

- Video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bOaPvR9Pgkw&ab_channel=DanielFredriksson

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ETHICAL STANDARDS

During the concert the audience was informed about the project and recordings before they entered the church. The video does not reveal any identity nor contain any personal data.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hartmut. Rosa. 2019. *Resonance: A Sociology of Our Relationship to the World*. Wiley, 111 River Street Hoboken, NJ. <https://books.google.se/books?id=0KjJvAEACAAJ>